

Development of a Cross-Platform Body Mass Index Calculator Using Flutter SDK

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Abstract: -

Body Mass index (BMI) is widely used metric to assess a person's health status based on height and weight. With the growth of mobile technologies, health related applications are increasingly prevalent. This paper presents the design and implementation of cross-platform BMI Calculator developed using flutter SDK. The application offers real time computation, a clean interface and supports both metric and imperial units. It leverages Dart programming for logic processing and Material Design principles for UI development. The project highlights Flutter's efficiency in developing health tools with single code base across iOS and Android.

1. Introduction

In the current era, mobile technology plays a crucial role in our daily lives, including health Monitoring. One of the most used tools in personal health care is Body Mass Index (BMI) Calculator. BMI is a simple metric derived from an individual's height and weight, used to classify Underweight, normal weight, over weight and obesity. This classification helps individuals monitor their physical health and take preventative or corrective actions when needed. With the proliferation of smartphones and app Development frameworks, creating health-based Applications has become more accessible. Flutter, developed by google, is an open source UI Software development kit that enables developers that build natively compiled applications for Mobile, web, and desktop from a single codebase. This paper presents the development of BMI Calculator

applications using Flutter SDK. The goal is to demonstrate how Flutter can be Leveraged to create an intuitive, real-time, cross-platform application that supports both metric And imperial units.

2. Problem statement

While there are numerous BMI apps available, many are limited by outdated interfaces, Platform restrictions, or lack of user-focused features. Some calculators provide results without context or Actionable advice. Others might be cluttered with advertisements or require internet access. Our application seeks to address these issues by offering a clean, offline-accessible, advertisement-Free experience with added interpretive support for users. It will allow users to calculate their BMI Means in terms of health status. The key problems addressed by this application include: Lack of cross platform availability Unclear or minimalistic feedback from BMI result Non-intuitive user interfaces Limited functionality in terms of unit selection and real-time results By resolving these issues, our BMI Calculator app aims to serve as a reliable, user-friendly and informative health tool.

3. Literature review

Many mobile health application have been emerged in recent years, targeting a wide array of Medical and health needs. BMI calculators are often a key feature within boarder fitness or healthtracking apps. These apps usually rely on native development, requiring separate code bases for Android and IOS which increases development effort and maintenance costs. Flutter with its widget- based reactive frame work and Dart programming language, provides anEfficient alternative. According to various studies, Flutter allows faster development seamless UIAcross platforms and better performance compared to hybrid framework like react native. A study by google says that Flutter significantly reduces development time and code reusabilityEspecially for startups and academic projects. Other research highlights the importance of intuitive interfaces in health apps. Users, particularly Adults are more likely to engage with applications that provide simple

navigation, clear output and minimal configuration. Thus, combining the power of Flutter with the principles of human-centered design can significantly enhance the utility and adoption of health applications like BMI calculators.

4. Methodology

Technology stack:

- Flutter SDK : UI tool kit for cross- platform development
- Dart: Programming language used for logic implementation
- Android studio: IDE for development and testing.
- Firebase(optional): for future extensions like saving user data

2. App architecture

- UI Layer: Designed using flutter widgets (ex: Text field, Elevated button).
- Logic layer: BMI is calculated using the formula:
$$\text{BMI} = \text{Weight}(\text{kg}) / \text{Height}(\text{m})^2$$
- Responsive Design: Layout adapts to screen sizes and orientations.

Project Resources:

System Architectural Flowchart:

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3:Features

-Input fields for height and weight

Toggle between metric and imperial units

Dynamic result display

Health categorization (underweight, normal, overweight, obese)

The project adopts an agile development methodology. Requirements are gathered through user Interviews and analysis of existing apps. Design wireframes were created using Figma then Implemented in Flutter. Testing involved both emulator and physical

device deployment to ensure

Responsive design

The BMI computation logic was kept modular to facilitate reusability. Internationalization was Considered for the future scalability into multi-language support. Accessibility features such as Font scaling and voice over compatibility were also considered to ensure Inclusivity.

5.Implementation

The BMI logic is implemented using a simple Dart function. The UI captures user inputs via Textfields and buttons. The BMI is recalculated in real time upon input change. The design Adheres to Material design standards for better UX consistency

Example code snippet:

```

'''dart
Double calculated BMI(double weight, double height) {
return weight / (height* height)
}
'''

```

UI highlights

Clean and minimal interface

Color-coded result based on BMI category

Platform consistent experience on both IOS and android. In addition to core features, the app Architecture follows the Model-View-Controller(MVC) Patterns to Separate UI, logic and data Management. The UI layer uses custom themes and animations for polished user experience.State management is handled being using 'SetState()' for Small scale interactivity with provision For integrating 'Provider' or 'Bloc' for future enhancements Error handling was added to manage valid inputs, and form validation ensures that height and Weight entries are within logical range. The BMI result screen dynamically displays the category

(Eg.'Normal weight') with color cues and health tips tailored to the result.

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6. Results

The application was tested across multiple Android and IOS devices. Results showed consistent Performance and accurate calculations. User feedback emphasized the app's simplicity, fast Response and aesthetic design.

Testing scenarios include unit testing of BMI logic, UI responsiveness on various screen sizes, and User testing.

The BMI calculations were validated against standard BMI Charts provided by World Health Organization. User survey were conducted to gather feedback on design, usability and Performance. 85% of testers rated the app as 'very easy to use' while 90% found the visual Output intuitive and helpful.

7. CONCLUSION

This project successfully demonstrates the capability of Flutter for building a responsive, cross- Platform BMI calculator. The app serves as a foundation for border health monitoring features Such as daily tracking, charts or integration with wearable devices. Our findings confirm that Flutter is an excellent tool for developing functional and user friendly cross-platform health Application. The app not only serves its primary function effectively but also sets a foundation For more complex health-monitoring tools in the future.

8. REFERENCES

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